

USE OF FOAMED POLYPROPYLENE FIBERS TO IMPROVE FIBER/MATRIX BOND FOR CEMENTITIOUS COMPOSITES

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Keywords: Fiber, Foam, Mortar, Adhesion, Pullout

ABSTRACT

Fibers are used in cementitious composites to improve some mechanical properties, i.e. toughness and tensile strength, and/or to avoid shrinkage cracking. For these purposes, fibers of different nature and shape are generally used: synthetic, natural, steel, smooth, crimped, hooked.

In composite materials the importance of fiber/matrix adhesion is widely recognized. To this extent, polyolefin fibers are chemical inert, relating to a cementitious matrix, and their surface is smooth thus leading to a low adhesion.

This work is aimed to improve fiber/matrix bond using polypropylene (PP) fibers with porous structure and improved surface roughness produced by a laboratory scale melt extrusion process using two different amounts (1 and 2 wt%) of a chemical foaming agent.

Density of fibers considerably decreases (from 0.91 g/cm³ of neat PP to 0.57 g/cm³ of foamed fibers). As shown by SEM images, the surface morphology of fibers, changes from smooth to highly rough at increasing the foaming agent content.

To evaluate fiber/matrix bond a cementitious mortar (one part of cement, three parts of sand and w/c of 0.55) has been prepared. Fiber/matrix adhesion was investigated by single fiber pull-out tests and SEM images which confirmed the increased mechanical bond of foamed fibers.

Usefulness of fibers against early age shrinkage cracking has been investigated using restrained mortar slabs. Increasing fibers volume fraction a reduction of cracks is observed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The last decades have seen an increasing use of fibers both in concrete and in mortar. The low tensile strength which characterizes cementitious materials can be improved by adding short randomly distributed fibers which can also reduce plastic shrinkage cracking. In the first instance, steel fibers or a high volume fraction of synthetic fibers are able to increase toughness and ductility of the composite material while in the latter fibers reduce cracks opening [1-5]. As well known, the effectiveness of fibers bridging across cracks and their mechanical reinforcing action is dependent on the fiber/matrix interactions. Thus, the key to improve properties of brittle materials using fibers lies on improving fiber/matrix bond. The role of interfacial bond between fibers and the cementitious matrix has been widely investigated with several kind of fibers. Generally polymeric fibers have a smooth surface resulting in a weak bond and a poor adhesion with the cementitious matrix. Consequently, to improve the composite properties is necessary to develop fibers with special features able to increase the interfacial bond [6].

Many researchers investigated several methods to have an interface strengthening by deforming fibers surface or modifying the chemical composition of the cement matrix. In the first case the aim is to increase the surface area of contact using crimped, twisted, fibrillated or embossed fibers [7-10]. In the latter a densification of the interface transition zone between fibers and matrix is achieved adding

silica fume or other fillers to the mix. The effects of these modifications on the composite are generally evaluated by fiber pullout tests [5, 7, 11].

The aim of this work is to increase the interaction between fibers and cementitious matrix by using fibers with rougher surface with improved interfacial bond. The optimization of volume fraction of such fibers in the cementitious matrix results in benefits for consistency, mechanical properties and shrinkage cracking resistance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

In this study, fibers with different composition and length were produced and characterized by means of morphological analyses and tensile tests.

In order to evaluate fiber/matrix bond, fibers were mixed into a cementitious mortar and the transition zone was characterized by SEM investigations. Bond strength was evaluated by pullout tests. Restrained shrinkage cracking tests were also conducted in order to evaluate the influence of fibers to control plastic shrinkage cracking.

2.1 Materials

Polypropylene (MOPLEN V79S, Montell Polyolefins) with a melt flow index of 2.1 g/10 min (230 °C, 2.16 kg) was used as polymer matrix.

To obtain foamed fibers, two different weight fractions, 1 and 2 wt.%, of chemical foaming agent (HYDROCEROL CF, Clariant Masterbatches Division) were used.

Thus, three different fibers were produced: pure polypropylene fibers (PP), foamed fibers with 1 and 2 wt.% of foaming agent (PP+1 % HCF and PP+2 % HCF respectively).

Mortar samples were prepared using one part of cement (CEM II A/LL 45.5 R, Italcementi Spa), three parts of sand (silica sand with grain size 0/2 mm) and w/c of 0.55.

2.2 Fibers production

Fibers were produced by a laboratory scale melt extrusion process using a single screw extruder (BRABENDER DO-CORDER E330, L/D = 24, capillary die of 1 mm) operating at the following temperature profile: 180°C-220°C-180°C, considering that the starting temperature of decomposition of the foaming agent is 150 °C. The foamed strand, was drawn and cooled in water and collected by a winder.

Processing temperature profile was the same for all the extrusions but different draw ratios were used in order to obtain fibers with a comparable diameter and an adequate surface roughness.

2.3 Fiber characterization

The diameter of fibers was evaluated by an optical microscope (Zeiss Axioskop 40). In the case of fibers with high roughness pictures were taken by a digital camera and then the profile was plotted to define a roughness coefficient (as described later on). Fibers density was measured by means of a gas pycnometer, using helium as gas. The average value of five measurements for each sample was taken as fiber density. Porosity of the cross section and surface roughness were determined by SEM images analysis.

Mechanical properties of fibers have been determined by tensile tests, according to ASTM C 1557-03 [12]. The tests were carried out at two cross-head speeds using a universal testing machine with a load cell of 1 kN (SANS CMT 6000). For each sample ten fibers were tested at a lower cross-head speed (4 mm/min) for determining elastic modulus (E) while other ten fibers were tested at a higher cross-head speed (40 mm/min) to evaluate tensile strength and strain at failure (σ_b and ϵ_b). Gauge length is 40 mm. Fibers physical and mechanical properties are listed in Table 2.

2.4 Fiber/matrix bond characterization

Mortar samples were prepared according to UNI EN 196-1 [13]. Fiber/matrix interface was investigated by SEM observations on the fracture surface of specimens cured for 28 days under water. Attention was paid to the presence of hydration products on the fiber surface and the matrix adhesion onto fibers.

The increase of fiber/matrix mechanical bond, was investigated by direct single fiber pull-out test. Two embedment lengths (10 and 20 mm) for each fiber were used and tested at a pullout rate of 1 mm/min. Pullout load versus displacement curves were obtained and the pullout strength measured.

2.5 Restrained plastic shrinkage cracking test

The influence of fibers type, length and volume fraction on plastic shrinkage cracking was evaluated by restrained cracking test [7]. Tests were performed for mortars containing PP and PP+2% HCF fibers, at three weight fractions (0.10, 0.25 and 0.50 %) and two lengths (15 and 30 mm). Specimens characteristics are reported in Table 1. Slabs of 50 x 50 x 5 cm restrained by angular steel profile were used in this test. After casting, specimens were taken for 8 hours in a climatic chamber with a fixed wind speed; weight, temperature and relative humidity were monitored each 30 minutes. The crack pattern of each specimen was observed and picture were taken every hour.

Mix	Fiber	Fiber length (mm)	Fiber wt.% (%)
Reference	-	-	-
FRM-PPA15	PP	15	0.10
FRM-PPB15	PP	15	0.25
FRM-PPC15	PP	15	0.50
FRM-PPA30	PP	30	0.10
FRM-PPB30	PP	30	0.25
FRM-PPC30	PP	30	0.50
FRM-FPPA15	PP+2% HCF	15	0.10
FRM-FPPB15	PP+2% HCF	15	0.25
FRM-FPPC15	PP+2% HCF	15	0.50
FRM-FPPA30	PP+2% HCF	30	0.10
FRM-FPPB30	PP+2% HCF	30	0.25
FRM-FPPC30	PP+2% HCF	30	0.50

Table 1: Specimens nomenclature for cracking test

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fiber characterization

Processing parameters were adapted to have fibers with comparable diameters and adequate surface roughness for foamed fibers. Due to foaming process, the radius of non-foamed fibers is only the 50% of the foamed one (Table 2).

Fibers density decreases of 38 % approximately, from 0.91 g/cm³ of neat PP to 0.57 g/cm³ of foamed fibers with 1 wt.% foaming agent. The density of fibers containing 2 wt.% of foaming agent is slightly higher and the density reduction is 27 %. The different density means a different porosity, i.e. a different cells morphology, considering that the diameter is more or less the same.

Fibers porosity was evaluated by computerized image analysis performed on SEM images taken on cryogenically broken fibers surface (Figure 1). The average area of cells is bigger for PP+1% HCF fibers while PP+2% HCF fibers have more voids but with a smaller average area. Moreover, also the cell distribution is different because in the first case the great part of porosity is concentrated in the middle of the fiber. The different cell morphology implies a different porosity. Image analyses

reported a porosity of 38 % and 16 % for PP+1 % HCF and PP+2 % HCF fibers respectively.

Figure 1: Fibers cross section: a) PP; b) PP+1% HCF and c) PP+2% HCF

Foam properties are largely linked to cellular morphology. Cell growth and stabilization, which are highly governed by the extensional rheology of polymer melt, influence the final foam structure. At the higher content of foaming agent a greater amount of yielded gas tends to migrate on the external surface of the fiber. In this case, an internal lower porosity and a rougher surface are obtained, as observed in Figure 1c. Moreover, elastic modulus and tensile strength of foamed fibers dramatically decrease (Table 2). The considered cross section for strength determination is the real cross section, i.e. net off porosity.

Fiber	Radius [mm]	Density [g/cm ³]	Elastic modulus [MPa]	Tensile strength [MPa]	Strain at failure [%]
PP	0.38	0.91	878	37	1400
PP+1% HCF	0.82	0.57	305	13	232
PP+2% HCF	0.84	0.66	316	19	816

Table 2: Fibers properties

The lower mechanical properties of fibers containing 1 wt.% of foaming agent are principally due to the higher porosity but also cells structure has an influence. Cells are oriented in the flow direction (Figure 2a) and during the tensile test cells walls are broken easier. Foamed fibers with 2 wt.% of foaming agent have a different longitudinal section: cells are not aligned in the flow direction and porous walls are thicker (Figure 2b). Such different morphology corresponds to a different mechanical behavior, resulting in a more ductile fibers because the influence of flow direction is negligible for cells structure. As reported in (Table 2) ϵ_b of PP+1 % HCF fibers is significantly lower respect PP+2 % HCF fibers (- 70 % approx.).

Figure 2: Fibers longitudinal section, 1 and 2 wt.% of foaming agent respectively

The different shape and surface texture of fibers has been investigated by SEM images. Figure 3 shows the smooth surface of PP fibers and the high surface roughness of fibers with 2 wt.% of foaming agent. PP+1 % HCF fibers (Figure 3b) were not considered in the second part of this study due to the lower roughness more comparable to the smoother PP fibers.

Figure 3: SEM images of fibers, a) PP, b) PP+1 % HCF and c) PP+2 % HCF fibers respectively

A further analysis of fibers profile has been carried out using images taken with a digital camera (Figure 4). A roughness coefficient could be defined in terms of profile linear roughness ratio, R_l , that is the ratio between the length of the profile line, L , and the projected length of the profile line, L_0 :

$$R_l = \frac{L}{L_0} \quad (1)$$

Figure 4: Fibers longitudinal sections: pure PP, 1 and 2 wt.% of foaming agent

The different roughness coefficients are reported in the following table (Table 3) considering the increase of roughness related to a perfectly smooth fiber with roughness equal to zero, like non foamed fibers.

Fiber	Roughness increase [%]
PP	-
PP+1% HCF	1
PP+2% HCF	16

Table 3: Increase of roughness respect non foamed fibers

As evident from images, the increase of roughness of PP+1% HCF fibers is very negligible. On the contrary, PP+2% HCF fibers show an increase of 16 % of the defined parameters.

3.2 Fiber/matrix bond characterization

The different surface textures result into different fiber/matrix interactions. First of all, PP fibers are completely separated from the cement paste (Figure 5a). Moreover, the low interaction implies also an increase of interface porosity (Figure 5b).

Figure 5: Interface transition zone between PP fiber and mortar

In the case of foamed fibers the different interface arrangement is clearly shown in Figure 6. The irregular surface represents an interlocking position for the cement paste, resulting in a better adhesion. Moreover, also mechanical bond is improved, as demonstrated by pullout tests.

Figure 6: Interface transition zone between PP+2% HCF fiber and mortar

Pullout tests confirmed the lower bond between PP fibers and the cementitious matrix. Figure 7 shows the pullout of a smooth PP fiber. Two embedment lengths were investigated to study the influence of this parameter on pullout behavior. The peak pullout load of PP fibers is significantly lower compared to the maximum pullout load of foamed fibers. Moreover, the pullout peak load increases with the fiber embedment length (Figure 8).

Figure 7: Pullout of PP fiber from the mortar

Figure 8: Maximum pullout load for the two embedment lengths (10 and 20 mm)

Fiber	Embedded length [mm]	F_{max} [N]
PP	10	2.85
	20	6.10
PP+1% HCF	10	12.85
	20	21.64
PP+2% HCF	10	19.28
	20	23.84

Table 4: Maximum pullout load varying embedded length

The improved behavior of foamed fibers can be recognized comparing pullout curves (Figure 9). For smooth fibers slipping occurs after the peak. On the other hand, foamed fibers, whose surface roughness offers interlocking positions, show higher adhesion to the cement paste. Thus, after the peak load, fibers start to be stretched. These phenomena have a key role for the behavior of the composite because determine the achievement of the maximum contribute of fibers. Moreover, the improved adhesion will results in a better fiber bridging during crack opening. As reported in Table 4, maximum pullout load for foamed fibers increases considerably particularly for PP+2% HCF fibers. The energy absorbed during pullout, i.e. the area under the pullout curve, represents the interfacial toughness. Considering the area up to 3 mm (before fibers start to be stretched) it is clear the remarkable increase of interfacial toughness.

Figure 9: Pullout curves, embedment length of a) 10 mm and b) 20 mm

3.3 Restrained plastic shrinkage cracking test

Fibers efficiency in controlling cracks opening during shrinkage is related to fiber length, volume fraction and surface morphology.

Time [h]	Crack characteristics	Mix		
		Reference	FRM-FPPB15	FRM-FPPB30
4	Number of cracks	61	62	24
	L_{max} [mm]	119.80	161.55	197.00
	W_{max} [mm]	2.00	1.70	1.25
6	Number of cracks	59	79	26
	W_{max} [mm]	222.65	223.05	339.80
	A_{max} [mm]	2.70	2.00	1.55
8	Number of cracks	48	59	31
	L_{max} [mm]	407.70	225.05	342.80
	W_{max} [mm]	2.70	2.05	1.55

Table 5: Example of crack analysis, a) Reference; b) FRM-FPP2B15; c) FRM-FPP2B30

As evident in Table 5, fibers are able to reduce cracks number, length (L_{max}), and width (W_{max}). Comparing specimens FRM-FPPB15 and FRM-FPPB30 (according to the nomenclature of Table 1) a clear influence of fibers length on the number of cracks and their width is recognizable. On the other hand, shorter fibers are influent on cracks length. For example the specimen FRM-FPPB30, after 8 hours of exposure, shows a reduction of cracks number (- 48%), length (- 16%) and width (- 43 %) respect the reference sample. The crack patterns of the Reference, FRM-FPPB15 and FRM-FPPB30 specimens, after 8 hours of exposure, are reported in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Example of crack pattern after 8 hours, a) Reference; b) FRM-FPP2B15; c) FRM-FPP2B30

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the foam extrusion process was carried out to manufacture polymeric fibers with improved adhesion with a cementitious matrix for the production of fiber reinforced mortars. Experimental investigations demonstrated that foam cell dimensions and distribution can be controlled by foaming agent content and processing conditions. In particular, fibers with adequate surface texture, suitable for mortar reinforcement, were obtained.

SEM images show the different interaction between a smooth fiber, i.e. PP fibers, and foamed fibers. The rougher surface gives rise to in a better fiber/matrix adhesion as confirmed by pullout tests which show a considerable increase of maximum pullout load and consequently interface toughness.

Pull out tests have shown that the use of fibers with a better mechanical bond implies a significant influence on total energy absorption due to the improved contact area.

The better adhesion of foamed fibers influenced the cracks development, particularly reducing crack area and delaying crack openings during shrinkage. Moreover, shorter fibers are better efficient in controlling cracks length while longer fibers are able to reduce cracks width and number.

The results of this study demonstrate the possibility to optimize fibers volume fraction in cementitious mortars using foamed fibers. Benefits could be not only in the control of plastic shrinkage cracking but also in the mechanical strength of the composite.

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